

Risk Factors for Abnormal Endometrium in Women with Perimenopausal Abnormal Uterine Bleeding

Rubeena Rasheed¹, Sajini B², Bindhu K M³

¹Junior Resident, Department of OBG, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala

²Professor, Department of OBG, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala

³Associate Professor, Department of OBG, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Rubeena Rasheed

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) is defined as deviation in normal menstrual cycle. Perimenopause is the age 2-8 years before and 1 year after final menses. This age group is more prone for anovulatory cycles.

Aim: To determine the factors associated with development of abnormal endometrial pathology in perimenopausal women with abnormal uterine bleeding at Kottayam medical college.

Objective: To determine the risk factors for abnormal endometrial pathology in perimenopausal women with abnormal uterine bleeding.

Methods: This is a prospective observational study conducted among 500 Perimenopausal women with AUB attending Gynecology Outpatient unit of Government medical college Kottayam from 30th September 2022 to 30th September 2023. Patients were evaluated. Endometrial sampling was done. Study variables assessed, includes BMI, Parity, Period of lactation, History of infertility, pcod, thyroid disease, diabetes mellites, Dyslipidemia etc. Odds ratio for each variable calculated. The study tool used was detailed Proforma. The data analysis was done using SPSS software version 20.

Results: 16% of the study population had endometrial pathology. High prevalence of AUB was found in subjects with a BMI corresponding to class I obesity. Around 81.8% of those with history of breast cancer. Presence of diabetes and hypertension showed similar results. Presence of thyroid disorders also showed 25.7% prevalence. Patients with dyslipidemia also showed a prevalence of 47.4%.

Conclusion: It was found that history of ART, PCOS had a protective effect on endometrium. History of breast cancer, Dyslipidaemia, diabetes, hypertension and thyroid disorders were found to be risk factors.

Keywords: Abnormal uterine bleeding, Body mass index, Oral contraceptive pills, In vitro fertilisation, Assisted reproductive technology, Polycystic ovarian syndrome, Intrauterine contraceptive devices, Coronary artery disease.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The average age of menopause in industrialised nations is 51 years, and depending on the elements involved, race, socioeconomic class, body mass index, and smoking status all seem to have an impact on this age by up to 2 years. [1]

During the perimenopause, also known as the menopausal transition, some women experience increase in menstrual flow, while others flow more sparingly. It is believed that these changes in menstrual flow during the transition phase indicate the approaching menopause and are connected to changes in sex hormone levels. [2]

But increase in monthly menstrual flow interfere with the women's physical, social and personal life which warrants evaluation of various risk factors

associated, the underlying pathology if any and proper management.

Studies shows that the most common cause of AUB in perimenopause is anovulation, leading to increased estrogenic environment that causes increased and irregular proliferation of endometrium leading to irregular menstrual bleeding. Unopposed estrogen exposure cause continued endometrial proliferation and potentially endometrial cancer.

Additionally, because there is no ovulation, the bleeding is unpredictable, which can have a negative effect on a woman's quality of life because she is constantly worried about unexpected bleeding. [3] Endometrial polyps, hyperplasia, and rarely endometrial carcinoma, may cause heavy

menstrual bleeding but also may present with intermenstrual bleeding. Large veins on the uterine surface of uterine fibroids, in particular submucous fibroids, may have enhanced vascularity and rupture during menstruation. Adenomyosis can cause heavy bleeding and dysmenorrhea [4]

It is frequently recommended that premenopausal women with heavy or irregular menstrual flow get an endometrial sample obtained to rule out endometrial illness.⁵ According to reports, premenopausal women have an incidence of endometrial hyperplasia ranging from 2% to 10%. [11] 10-20% of endometrial cancer occurs before menopause and most of them are aged between 40-50. [6] The endometrium can exhibit abnormalities ranging from hyperplasia to aggressive malignancy. Endometrial hyperplasia is a precursor to endometrial cancer, and over the course of a 13-year period, 3% to 23% of instances with complicated hyperplasia can proceed to endometrial cancer without treatment. [7]

Identification of risk factors for endometrial hyperplasia in premenopausal women may result in decrease in the number of women who undergo diagnostic testing. Although the risk factors for endometrial hyperplasia in postmenopausal women has well been established, they do not necessarily apply to premenopausal women, and only few reports have focused on this group of women.⁸ The objective of this study was to identify risk factors for endometrial pathology including endometrial hyperplasia, endometrial carcinoma and other pathology like endometrial polyp in premenopausal women with abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB). The goal of management will depend upon the etiological diagnosis. The history, physical and pelvic examination help determine the site and source of bleeding. Information from this will suggest on further investigations such as ultrasound and histopathology. Ultrasound gives information about the structure of uterus and ovaries including endometrial thickness. Endometrial biopsy is taken by dilatational curettage, pipelle aspiration of endometrium or hysteroscopy. The obtained tissue is then subjected to histopathological examination. Histopathology of hysterectomy specimen can also be assessed for abnormal endometrium.

Objective: To determine the risk factors for abnormal endometrial pathology in perimenopausal abnormal uterine bleeding.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Government Medical college, Kottayam for a period of one year from September 2022 after getting approval from Institutional Review Board (IRB No:77/2022). It was a prospective observational study.

Sample Size

$$N = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 P Q}{D^2}$$

The sample size was calculated according to study by Farquhar, C. M et al in 1999, "An evaluation of risk factors for endometrial hyperplasia in premenopausal women with abnormal menstrual bleeding". [14] The prevalence of nulliparity [6], substituting it in the equation the sample size is calculated as 500.

$$P \{\text{Proportion of nulliparity in study group}\} = 16$$

$$Q \{100-P\} = 79$$

$$D \{\text{Absolute proportion}\} = 20/100 \times 21 = 4.2$$

$$z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 = 1.96$$

Study Population: perimenopausal women with abnormal uterine bleeding undergone clinical and histopathological evaluation for the same in kottayam medical college.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age between 42-50 yrs
2. patients with endocrine disorders and hypertensive disorders
3. Patients with other known cancers.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with chronic liver or renal disease.
2. Women with coagulation disorders.
3. Women on progesterone therapy for abnormal uterine bleeding.

Study Tool: A structured detailed proforma will be used to gather the essential information of the factors under study. Proforma filled by the principal investigator. Data form included in the annexure.

Study Procedure: The study will begin after the approval from institutional review board. The study prospective observational study. Women of premenopausal age group with abnormal uterine bleeding will be selected.

Patients will be evaluated by their history of complaints and past history of comorbidities, clinical examination, and investigations such as blood tests, ultrasonography and histopathology of endometrial samples taken via hysteroscopy, dilatation and curettage or pipelle aspiration of endometrium.

Various study variables will be assessed here, that includes

1. BMI
2. Parity
3. Period of lactation
4. History of infertility
5. History of pcod

6. Endocrine disorders- thyroid disease, diabetes mellites,
7. Dyslipidemia
8. Long term use of oral contraceptive pills and intrauterine non-hormonal contraceptive devices
9. Other malignancies including breast, colorectal, thyroid, lung cancers
10. Other associated abnormal Usg findings ovarian pathology, fibroid, adenomyosis.

Odds ratio for each variable calculated and risk assessed.

Data Management and Analysis: Data will be entered into Microsoft Excel sheet and data analysis will be done with SSPS – 25. Categorical variables will be expressed as proportions and continuous variables will be expressed as mean and standard deviation.

Statistical tests of significance will be analysed using Chi Square test; $p < 0.05$ will be considered significant.

Results

Age Distribution among Perimenopausal AUB Patients

Table 1: Distribution of patients with AUB according to their age

Abnormal Endometrium	Age(Years)	
	Not present	Mean
	Median	44.00
	Std. Deviation	2.081
	Minimum	42
	Maximum	50
Present	Mean	43.77
	Median	43.00
	Std. Deviation	1.587
	Minimum	42
	Maximum	49

The study shows that most of the study subjects were around 43-44 yrs of age. Among those with endometrial pathology, most of the subjects were of 43 yrs. The study population was of 42-50 yrs aged

women, and the max age at which endometrial pathology was detected was 49 yrs.

Dyslipidaemia

Table 2: Association between dyslipidaemia and abnormal endometrium

Abnormal Endometrium	Dyslipidemia	Frequency	
		Present	Not present
Not present	Not present	382	90.5
	Present	40	9.5
	Total	422	100.0
Present	Not present	42	53.8
	Present	36	46.2
	Total	78	100.0

Thyroid Disorders

Table 3: Association between thyroid disorders and abnormal endometrium

Abnormal Endometrium	Thyroid disorders	Frequency	
		Percent	Frequency
Not Present	Not present	74.6	315
	Present	25.4	107
	Total	100.0	422
Present	Not present	52.6	41
	Present	47.4	37
	Total	100.0	78

IVF

Table 4: Association between IVF and abnormal endometrium

Abnormal Endometrium	IVF	Frequency	
		Percent	Frequency
Not Present	Not present	88.2	372
	Present	11.8	50
	Total	100.0	422

Present	Not present	76	97.4
	Present	2	2.6
	Total	78	100.0

IUCD

Table 5: Association between IUCD use and abnormal endometrium

Abnormal Endometrium	IUCD	Frequency	Percent
Not present	Not Present	385	91.2
	Present	37	8.8
	Total	422	100.0

Hypertension

Table 6: Association between abnormal endometrium and hypertension

Abnormal Endometrium	Hypertension	Frequency	Percent
Not present	Not present	207	49.1
	Present	215	50.9
	Total	422	100.0
Present	Not present	31	39.7
	Present	47	60.3
	Total	78	100.0

Diabetes

Table 7: Association between diabetes and abnormal endometrium

Abnormal Endometrium	Diabetes	Frequency	Percent
Not present	Not present	227	53.8
	Present	195	46.2
	Total	422	100.0
Present	Not present	39	50.0
	Present	39	50.0
	Total	78	100.0

Abnormal Endometrium – Breast Cancer

Table 8: Association between breast cancer and abnormal endometrium

			Abnormal Endometrium		Total
			Present	Absent	
Breast Cancer	Present	Frequency	9	2	11
		Percentage	81.8%	18.2%	100.0%
	Absent	Frequency	69	420	489
		Percentage	14.1%	85.9%	100.0%
Total		Frequency	78	422	500
		Percentage	15.6%	84.4%	100.0%

Fisher’s Exact test, P value – 0.001

Abnormal Endometrium – Hypertension

Table 9: Association between hypertension and abnormal endometrium

			Abnormal Endometrium		Total
			Present	Absent	
Hypertension	Present	Frequency	47	215	262
		Percentage	17.9%	82.1%	100.0%
	Absent	Frequency	31	207	238
		Percentage	13.0%	87.0%	100.0%
Total		Frequency	78	422	500
		Percentage	15.6%	84.4%	100.0%

Chi- Square – 2.3, P Value -0.13

Abnormal Endometrium – Thyroid Disorder**Table 10: Association between thyroid disorder and abnormal endometrium**

			Abnormal Endometrium		Total
			Present	Absent	
Thyroid disorder	Present	Frequency	37	107	144
		Percentage	25.7%	74.3%	100.0%
	Absent	Frequency	41	315	356
		Percentage	11.5%	88.5%	100.0%
Total		Frequency	78	422	500
		Percentage	15.6%	84.4%	100.0%

Chi-Square – 15.7, P Value -0.001

Table 11: Association between Abnormal Endometrium – Dyslipidaemia

			Abnormal Endometrium		Total
			Present	Absent	
Dyslipidemia	Present	Frequency	36	40	76
		Percentage	47.4%	52.6%	100.0%
	Absent	Frequency	42	382	424
		Percentage	9.9%	90.1%	100.0%
Total		Frequency	78	422	500
		Percentage	15.6%	84.4%	100.0%

Chi-Square – 68.7, P Value -0.001

Discussion

The study was conducted on perimenopausal women who came to gynaecology out-patient (OP) unit of government with complaints of abnormal uterine bleeding, to assess risk factors among those women who developed endometrial pathology. Endometrial biopsy was done out of which 1 of the participants had endometrial cancer. The mean age of the subjects was 43 years. High prevalence of AUB was found in subjects with a BMI corresponding to class I obesity, with mean BMI around 26kg/m². But its association as a risk factor could not be substantiated through this study. Hence its association could not be established with this study.

A prevalence of 17.5% was seen in those who did not use OCP in their life when compared to those who had a history of ocp use that was 3.1% only. Around 81.8% of those subjects with history of breast cancer developed abnormal endometrium when compared to those without breast cancer which was 14%. This was consistent with the finding by Maria L et al on study 'Risk Factors Associated with Endometrial Pathology in Premenopausal Breast Cancer Patients Treated with Tamoxifen' which showed that premenopausal breast cancer patients on tamoxifen are at a higher risk in developing endometrial cancer. [9]

Presence of diabetes and hypertension showed similar results. Around 17% of those with the history of diabetes and hypertension each showed increased risk of endometrial pathology when compared to those who did not have those comorbidities. This was consistent with findings by

Vasilios P et al on 'systemic hypertension and diabetes mellitus as predictors of malignancy among women with endometrial polyps' which concluded that both diabetes and systemic hypertension seem to be correlated with increased odds of developing premalignant and malignant endometrial polyps. [10] Similar studies were done by Cohen C J on 'endometrial cancer management of high risk and recurrence' also showed similar results for diabetes but systemic hypertension was not found as independent variable for concluding it as a risk factor. [11] Study done by Ana M on 'factors associated with endometrial cancer and hyperplasia among middle aged and older Hispanics' also found similar results. Presence of thyroid disorders also showed 25.7% prevalence of endometrial disorder in subjects while those with normal thyroid status showed a prevalence of 11.5% of endometrial disorders. [12] Hence thyroid disorders were found to be a risk factor and was positively associated with the development of endometrial diseases. A study done in The USA by Kang J H on 'A Large Cohort Study of Hypothyroidism and Hyperthyroidism in Relation to Gynecologic Cancers' showed that history of hypothyroidism for > or = 8 years (median) was non-significantly inversely associated with endometrial cancer and Ovarian cancer and having a history of hyperthyroidism for > or = 6 years (median) was non-significantly positively associated with Endometrial cancer. [13]

History of dyslipidemia also showed a prevalence of 47.4% of endometrial disease while those with normal lipid profile had a prevalence of 15.6%. Similar study done by Lee D Y on associations

between metabolic syndrome and gynecologic cancer showed that each component of Metabolic syndrome a (type 2 diabetes, obesity, dyslipidaemia and hypertension) and associated metabolic disarrangements are proved to have a correlation with cancer development through experimental studies. [14] However, was not clear whether the effects of each component are additive or synergistic. A study done by Xiao Y showed that metabolic syndrome was closely related to prognosis of endometrial cancer. [15]

Recommendations

1. To assess all the risk factors in perimenopausal women with AUB and categorize the patients into low and high risk for endometrial pathology along with treating other components of AUB concurrently.
2. To create awareness regarding importance of risk reduction, thereby prevention of endometrial cancer.
3. To recommend endometrial sampling to all women with perimenopausal AUB especially in women belonging to high risk category.

Limitations

Through this study association between endometrial pathology and factors such as BMI, breast feeding, CAD, IUCD use and parity couldn't be substantiated and can be attributed possibly to convenient sampling.

In this study group none of the women had history of smoking, alcohol, substance abuse or colorectal cancer. Hence the association of these factors could not be studied.

Conclusion

The study concludes that prevalence of abnormal endometrium in perimenopausal women with AUB was 16 percent and mean age was around 43 years. 1 person among 500 subjects was found to have endometrial carcinoma endometrioid type-low grade. Majority of the women in the study group were married and sexually active women. Among these women prevalence of endometrial disease was around 17%. 56 women in study group were unmarried and sexually inactive. All of these women had a normal endometrium on histopathology. BMI, breastfeeding, parity, CAD and IUCD use did not show any association with development of abnormal uterine bleeding in this study. It was found that history of ART, PCOS had a protective effect on endometrium. There was a lower incidence of endometrial disease in these women when compared to those who did not have positive history. History of breast cancer was found to be a risk factor for the disease. Majority of the women with history of breast cancer in the study were on Tamoxifen and were on follow up in oncology unit. Dyslipidaemia, diabetes,

hypertension and thyroid disorders were found to be risk factors.

References

1. Hallberg L, Högdahl AM, Nilsson L, Rybo G. Menstrual blood loss--a population study. Variation at different ages and attempts to define normality. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.* 1966; 45(3):320-51. .
2. Cutler WB, Friedmann E, McCoy NL. Coitus and menstruation in perimenopausal women. *J Psychosom Obstet Gynaecol.* 1996 Sep; 17(3):149-57.
3. Nesse RE. Abnormal vaginal bleeding in perimenopausal women. *Am Fam Physician.* 1989 Jul; 40(1):185-92.
4. Farrell E. Dysfunctional uterine bleeding. *Aust Fam Physician.* 2004 Nov; 33(11):906-8.
5. Ash SJ, Farrell SA, Flowerdew G. Endometrial biopsy in DUB. *J Reprod Med.* 1996 Dec; 41(12):892-6.
6. Gallup DG, Stock RJ. Adenocarcinoma of the endometrium in women 40 years of age or younger. *Obstet Gynecol.* 1984 Sep; 64(3):417-20.
7. Hunter JE, Tritz DE, Howell MG, DePriest PD, Gallion HH, Andrews SJ, Buckley SB, Kryscio RJ, van Nagell JR Jr. The prognostic and therapeutic implications of cytologic atypia in patients with endometrial hyperplasia. *Gynecol Oncol.* 1994 Oct; 55(1):66-71.
8. Farquhar CM, Lethaby A, Sowter M, Verry J, Baranyai J. An evaluation of risk factors for endometrial hyperplasia in premenopausal women with abnormal menstrual bleeding. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 1999 Sep; 181(3):525-9.
9. Lee M, Piao J, Jeon MJ. Risk Factors Associated with Endometrial Pathology in Premenopausal Breast Cancer Patients Treated with Tamoxifen. *Yonsei Med J.* 2020 Apr; 61(4):317-322.
10. Pergialiotis V, Prodromidou A, Siotos C, Frountzas M, Perrea D, Vlachos GD. Systemic hypertension and diabetes mellitus as predictors of malignancy among women with endometrial polyps: a meta-analysis of observational studies. *Menopause.* 2016 Jun; 23(6):691-7.
11. Cohen CJ, Rahaman J. Endometrial cancer. Management of high risk and recurrence including the tamoxifen controversy. *Cancer.* 1995 Nov 15; 76(10 Suppl):2044-52.
12. Rodriguez AM, Polychronopoulou E, Hsu E, Shah R, Lamiman K, Kuo YF. Factors associated with endometrial cancer and hyperplasia among middle-aged and older Hispanics. *Gynecol Oncol.* 2021 Jan; 160(1):16-23.
13. Kang JH, Kueck AS, Stevens R, Curhan G, De Vivo I, Rosner B, Alexander E, Tworoger SS. A large cohort study of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism in relation to gynecologic

- cancers. *Obstet Gynecol Int.* 2013; 2013:74-3721.
14. Lee DY, Lee TS. Associations between metabolic syndrome and gynecologic cancer. *Obstet Gynecol Sci.* 2020May; 63(3):215-224.
 15. Yang X, Wang J. The Role of Metabolic Syndrome in Endometrial Cancer: A Review. *Front Oncol.* 2019 Aug 8; 9:744.